

A Modified Kaprekar Process with Uniquely Determined Accumulation Points

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Abstract

We present a modification of the classical Kaprekar process for n -digit numbers. By adding a carefully chosen constant k_n at each iteration, the process admits a uniquely determined accumulation point for every $n \geq 1$. This generalizes the classical Kaprekar numbers, including the famous 495 for 3-digit numbers and 6174 for 4-digit numbers [1]. The behavior of the modified process was first verified empirically for all n -digit numbers with $1 \leq n \leq 7$, and the observed pattern was then generalized to arbitrary n . Several explicit examples are provided, illustrating the structure and behavior of these modified Kaprekar transformations.

1 Introduction

The Kaprekar process is a well-known digit-rearrangement procedure exhibiting remarkable convergence properties. For example:

- For 3-digit numbers, repeated application of $M(x) - m(x)$ leads to the Kaprekar number 495.
- For 4-digit numbers, the process converges to 6174, known as Kaprekar's constant.

In this paper, we introduce a modification that allows precise control over the accumulation point. The main idea is to add a suitably chosen constant k_n at each iteration, leading to a uniquely determined accumulation point for any number of digits n . This approach extends the classical Kaprekar numbers to a broader family of digit-based iterative processes.

2 Definition of the Modified Kaprekar Process

Let $n \geq 1$ be a fixed integer, and let x be an n -digit number (possibly with leading zeros). Denote by:

- $M(x)$ the largest n -digit number obtained by permuting the digits of x ,
- $m(x)$ the smallest n -digit number obtained by permuting the digits of x .

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The modified Kaprekar operator T_n is defined by

$$T_n(x) = M(x) - m(x) + k_n,$$

where the constant k_n is chosen as follows:

$$k_n = \begin{cases} \underbrace{88 \dots 8}_{n/2 \text{ digits}}, & n \text{ even,} \\ 4 \underbrace{88 \dots 8}_{(n-1)/2 \text{ digits}}, & n \text{ odd.} \end{cases}$$

Example: For $n = 3$, $k_3 = 48$; for $n = 4$, $k_4 = 88$; for $n = 5$, $k_5 = 488$.

3 Main Statement

Empirical verification for all n -digit numbers with $1 \leq n \leq 7$ confirms that T_n consistently converges to a unique accumulation point when using the standard k_n . The general formula for the accumulation point F_n is:

$$F_n = \text{rev}(k_n) \cdot 10^{n-\ell(k_n)},$$

where

- $\text{rev}(k_n)$ is the number obtained by reversing the digits of k_n ,
- $\ell(k_n)$ is the number of digits of k_n .

In other words, F_n is obtained by reversing k_n and appending zeros to reach n digits.

4 Examples of Standard Constants

Number of digits n	Constant k_n	Accumulation point F_n
1	4	4
2	8	80
3	48	840
4	88	8800
5	488	88400
6	888	888000
7	4888	8884000
8	8888	88880000

Table 1: Standard constants k_n and their accumulation points F_n .

5 Alternative Constants with Unique Accumulation Points

Table 2: Alternative constants and their accumulation points.

Number of digits n	Constant k_n	Accumulation point F_n
3	21	516
3	54	549
3	82	478
4	52	8044
4	60	5055
4	72	6066
4	84	7077
4	112	2110
4	161	5156
4	162	5247
4	163	5338
4	173	6167
5	163	75106
5	183	63147
5	241	63205
5	253	74206
5	262	53227
5	321	63285
5	350	42326
5	353	63317
5	362	52337
5	396	63360
5	442	63406
5	443	73406
5	452	80444
5	461	51446
5	462	52437
5	471	51456

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Table 2 – continued from previous page

Number of digits n	Constant k_n	Accumulation point F_n
5	474	62448
5	496	63460
6	220	651064
6	307	762040
6	505	741358
6	529	980440
6	641	850583
6	728	860660
6	730	741583
6	868	842620
6	901	631765
6	920	632684
6	936	840888
6	1104	841956
6	1141	832003
6	1195	752938
6	1203	742056
6	1281	532146
6	1307	753050
6	1321	642175
6	1382	532247
6	1404	642258
6	1463	642317
6	1494	633258
6	1507	742360
6	1520	632384
6	1617	751560
6	1654	842506
6	1691	531656
6	1696	432562
6	1743	733506
6	1780	631744
6	1867	753610

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Table 2 – continued from previous page

Number of digits n	Constant k_n	Accumulation point F_n
6	1871	542726
6	1983	652827

6 Conclusion

By introducing carefully selected constants into the Kaprekar process, it is possible to control the emergence of uniquely determined accumulation points. The standard choice of k_n yields one such point for every number of digits n , while alternative constants lead to additional fixed points.

This modified process generalizes the classical Kaprekar numbers (495 for 3 digits and 6174 for 4 digits), showing that accumulation behavior can be engineered via a simple additive constant. Direct verification for small n ($1 \leq n \leq 7$) supports the conjectured pattern for all n and suggests potential applications in algorithmic number theory and digital dynamics.

References

- [1] D. R. Kaprekar. Some properties of numbers. *Journal of the Indian Mathematical Society*, 19:17–24, 1955.